

SOCIOLOGY
ETHNOLOGY
BULLETIN

Volume I

Number 2

March 1992

CONTENTS

Editors' Preface		3
I. NORTH AND SOUTH OMO		
Our visit to the Gamo highlands and the elders' blessings in Doko market <i>Getie Gelaye</i>		4
A glimpse at Konso markets: the case of Bägawlé, <i>Ayalew Gebre</i>		9
The death and burial of Kalla Qñhazmach Kayoté, a ritual leader of the Konso people of southern Ethiopia, <i>Tadesse Wolde</i>		12
Resource use in Konso, <i>Tejari Abate</i>		22
Traditional defence among the Konso of Ethiopia, <i>Bekalu Molla</i>		26
<i>Gülla</i> and <i>Gohwar</i> : seasonal ceremonies from the cultural heritage of Wolayta, <i>Altoye Alaro</i>		29
The politico-legal function of the <i>halaga</i> among the Dorzé, <i>Mirgisa Kaba</i>		32
The Mago park and the people in its vicinity: conflict or coexistence? <i>Girmaye Kebede</i>		35
Some steps in the planning of a research centre at Jinka, South Omo, <i>Ivo Strecker</i> , with postscripts by <i>Gebre Yritiso</i> and <i>Abula Pankhurst</i>		41
II. DISPUTE SETTLEMENT AND RECONCILIATION		
Institutional forgiveness in Borana assemblies, <i>Marco Bassi</i>		50
Conflict resolution in traditional Amhara society, <i>Solomon Gebre</i>		55
Peace negotiations in the land of Däwaro in 1531: a page from the history of Ahmäd Grañ, <i>Richard Pankhurst</i>		61
<i>Gondaro</i> : a ritual of conflict resolution in Wolayta, <i>Tsehai Berhane-Selassie</i>		65
Gender and power: male and female in a Me'en homicide compensation ceremony, <i>Jon Abbink</i>		67
Settling strife in a resettlement setting: symbolic sanctions?, <i>Abula Pankhurst</i>		73
III. OTHER CONTRIBUTIONS		
The job: medicine or sacrifice? <i>Jean Lydall</i>		80
Hyena porridge: ethnographic filming in the walled city of Harär, <i>Ahmed Zekaria</i>		86
<i>Ch'it</i> in popular culture: a "prayer" from Harär, Ethiopia, <i>Jon Abbink</i>		89
Filming dreams, <i>Ivo Strecker</i>		94
Anthropology and history at Addis Ababa: University: the need for collaboration, <i>Shiferaw Bekele</i>		98
Bibliography of Senior Essays of the Department of History, Addis Ababa University, on ethno-historical and related topics, <i>Shiferaw Bekele</i>		102

Editors

Ahula Pankhurst
Tsehai Berhane-Selassie

Editorial Committee

Ahmed Zekaria
Brutawit Fekade
Getie Gelaye
Hirut Terefe
Mengistu Seyoum
Mirgisa Kaba
Solomon Gebre
Worku Nida

Price

Ethiopia: 5 Ethiopian Birr
Outside Ethiopia: 5 US dollars.

The *Sociology Ethnology Bulletin of Addis Ababa University* is a publication initiated by the Department of Sociology and Social Administration, in collaboration with the Institute of Ethiopian Studies.

The editors wish to thank the Cooperative Project in Social Anthropology for generous assistance with publication costs. All photographs are by Ivo Strecker unless otherwise indicated.

Address for contributions and information:

The Editors, SEB,
Department of Sociology and Social Administration,
Addis Ababa University,
P.O. Box 1176 Addis Ababa,
Ethiopia.

Cover picture: View through a Konso gateway, photo: Bernhard Strecker.

INSTITUTIONAL FORGIVENESS IN BORANA ASSEMBLIES

Marco Bassi⁵¹

In 1986 I had the pleasure of spending one year with the Borana of Northern Kenya. Bante Abbagala, a *jallaaba abbaa qa'ee* i.e. a traditional leader, became one of my closest friends. Because of his title he is able to organise local meetings and he usually attends his clan assemblies which are held each year in Ethiopia. Bante explained to me that offenders are punished with a fine the amount of which is established in the context of assemblies according to traditional law, and that the penalty can be as high as thirty cows.

The Borana do not dispose of any means of imposing decisions by force and I was therefore intrigued by the following simple question: why do people accept to pay such high fines if nobody can force them to do so? How can you, I then asked Bante, force people to accept a punishment when they are condemned at one of the local meetings you organise? He replied that, if they don't accept the penalty, he would bring the matter to the attention of the *hyyuu* (clan leaders of authority higher than *jallaaba*) so that the case can be discussed at the next clan assembly.

All the *hyyuu* live in the Borana homelands, in Ethiopia, and it is only there that the Borana organise their clan assemblies. I was anxious, therefore, to have an opportunity to continue my research in Ethiopia. This became possible when, in 1989, the Institute of Ethiopian Studies of Addis Ababa University approved my application to become a Visiting Scholar, and assisted me through a new cycle of research among the Borana of Ethiopia.

The problem of the enforcement of assembly decisions continued to puzzle me for a long time. None of my friends and informants I approached in the field expressed any doubt about the great authority of traditional leaders. Even some administrators whom I would have expected to emphasise the role of the central power, openly declared that not only did they allow, but they even encouraged the resolution of conflicts within the traditional system, provided of course that the matter did not pertain to issues concerning the government, such as taxation, smuggling and so on.

But on what is the authority of traditional leadership based? To investigate the point I proceeded with questions like the following: "If you do something wrong, and the assembly fines you and you do not pay, what happens?" The common reply was: "How can you refuse to pay if the assembly orders you to do so?" However, it was also explained to me that it is actually possible to avoid payment, but that would mean cutting off all relations with the clan. The final comment was: "How can you live without the clan?" This reply supports Paul Baxter's explanation of the nature of authority in Borana. He explains it in terms of exclusion from *Nagaa Boranaana*, "The Peace of the Borana", a fundamental concept with both ritual and sociological implications.

position the people of Jinka wish to bestow upon their centre. We heard that hotel builders had their eyes on this site which could also have been designated the location for the municipality, a hospital or any other important civic building.

Together with members of the town committee and of the town planning department we surveyed the site and began to think about such things as the boundaries of the centre, the orientation of the site, an access path and road from the town, as well as tentative ideas for the location of the museum, library, cafeteria, guest house, auditorium, etc. All those we met were excited about the scheme and eagerly shared their ideas with us. We learnt that the town planners have decided to preserve the hillside around the site as a "green belt", which will conserve the remarkable scenic beauty of the hillside, with its traditional Ari housing style surrounded by groves of *ensit*, coffee and banana trees.

View from Jinka Town towards the proposed site for SORC (Photo: Alula Pankhurst)

It was decided that the boundaries of the SORC site would be marked on the town plan and that a first step would be to employ gardeners to plant hedges and trees. Earlier contributions were found in the special bank account opened for the project a year ago and the committee started to collect further individual donations. The Committee also began working out the details of local contributions, which will include road-building, installation of electricity, water and drainage facilities, a store and garage, and the collection of materials and artifacts. Teachers reported that school children, who come from all parts of the region, are eager to devote time and energy to the project.

Before leaving Jinka we also considered various local building materials which could be used in construction; in particular we were excited by the possibility of using a white marble-like stone located at Qaqa some 30 kilometres away. We began to envisage an attractive facade for the museum, visible from the town below. Since our return to Addis Ababa we have tried to think out some details of the plan which Fasil is turning into a design to present to funders.

⁵¹ Visiting scholar from Istituto Orientale di Napoli, currently writing up his Ph.D. research on the Borana.

To be excluded from the Peace means to be excluded also from community co-operation. As Baxter says, in an environment such as that of the Borana "no man nor family can exist for long as a social, herding or ritual isolate"⁵², which is exactly what was claimed by my friend. In this sense the pressure of the community on its members may be very effective. However thirty cows are a considerable amount, especially nowadays since the average availability has greatly decreased, and I still could not entirely believe that an offender could be induced to pay such high fines even if he were ordered by a traditional leader in an assembly. Nor was I convinced by the description of *jirfu* punishment (*jirfu* literally means "gut of the spear"), consisting of removing cows forcibly from the cattle enclosure by men entrusted to do so at the clan assembly. *Jirfu*, in fact, is only applicable when a man resists delivering a cow to a poor clan-mate needing assistance.

As time went on I realised that I could not collect even a single case of either *jirfu* being performed or a large fine been actually paid. I could only register some reports regarding the payment of small compensations, at most one or two cows. This gap between the statements regarding punishments and reality arose in a paradigmatic way during a visit to Guyyo Kosu, an old and active *huyyu* of the Diigalu clan.

When I arrived he was engaged in a conversation, commenting on a case of conflict just settled. Quressa, the brother of Guyyo's interloctor, had led his mare and colt to drink at a pond which, at that stage of the dry season, had been reserved for human consumption only. For this reason he was fined by the leader of the *qabbale* (a Peasant Association, the minimum state administrative unit in rural areas) fined him. Two cows were taken out of his cattle-enclosure, which the leader of the *qabbale* intended to sell at the market. Quressa asked for assistance from the most prestigious traditional leaders in the area, two *huyyus* one of whom was Guyo Kosu, the *qallu* of the Gajji lineage. A public meeting was then called, during which it was established that the *qabbale* leader was wrong. Even if Quressa had made a mistake, it was said, the matter did not concern the *qabbale*. Guyyo Kosu explained to me that during the last *Gumi Gayo* (the general assembly of the Borana held every eight years) it was agreed by both Borana leaders and local state administrators that the problems of the Borana must first be discussed by the Borana leadership in the traditional way.

Horses have a great symbolic value for the Borana and their husbandry is regulated by a very complex corpus of traditional norms and laws, known in its entirety only by experts (particularly among members of the *Macc'hitu* clan). The *qabbale* has no such competence concerning horses and therefore the leader of the Peasant Association was fined thirty cows for each one taken from Quressa! In telling the case Guyyo could not hide his satisfaction for having been able to impose his authority on a *qabbale* leader. Indeed I was also very surprised. So I went on, and I asked Quressa's brother if they actually had received the 60 cows. Both he and Guyyo Kosu laughed at the question, explaining that in fact only the two cows taken by force were actually returned.

⁵² P. T. W. Baxter, 1990, p. 238.

It became clear that even if elders continue to speak in terms of big fines, these are actually lowered or even canceled. However, the mechanisms of penalty reduction still escaped my understanding. I thought that, lacking any physical coercive means, the fine is somehow suspended, or only partially paid, until it is finally 'forgotten'. Later on, during a clan assembly, I realised that this assumption was false.

At that clan assembly (an important meeting which can last more than one month) the main theme under discussion was the collection of money or cows for the digging of a new well. At some point the oldest *huyyu* introduced a new problem to the audience. A few months earlier a dispute concerning cows had arisen between two men named Anna and Guyyo. Both of them belonged to the same clan and were attending the meeting. The *huyyu* was called in order to give a judgement on the matter. His sentence was against Anna, but the latter refused to accept it. It was thus that the same *huyyu* was now submitting the whole matter to the clan. After his introduction, many elders spoke, including the two protagonists, Anna and Guyyo.

The whole situation was elucidated and discussed in detail by the two sides. When time for a final judgement approached, Anna declared that this time he was ready to accept any decision, since the attending *itcho* (literally riding-whip, a symbol of authority held by *huyyu* and other prestigious leaders) were three, instead of only one (implying that there was less room for arbitrary judgments). Immediately following that statement one of the elders declared that Anna behaved wrongly. At this point the *huyyu*, whose judgment had been rejected, gave way to a highly rhetoric speech, referring to the source of his authority and to his knowledge of traditional law (actually it was an answer to Anna's allusion to 'arbitrary sentences').

The speech was interrupted by a sudden action of Anna: he grasped a tuft of grass, ran to the place where the *huyyu* was sitting and, putting the grass near his feet, repeated "*Abbaa na baa, daraara*" many times and loudly. The first part can be translated "Father forgive me", whereas *daraara* (literally "to flower" or "to blossom") is a word which accompanies some common ritual acts of prayer or blessing. Request of forgiveness obviously implies pleading guilty. All the assembly burst into laughter, whilst Anna, in a ridiculous attitude, continued to pick grass offering it to Guyyo, the man who was originally offended, and to other elders, repeating "*daraara*".

At this point the *huyyu* gave the sentence, explaining that the offence must be punished, according to the law, with ten cows to be given to the *huyyu*, five cows to the *jallaaba*, plus one for the digging of the well and one for Guyyo, the offended man. The debate went on until - and here the phase of penalty-reduction comes in - a *jallaaba* suggested that, Anna having preemptively declared that he would accept the assembly decision, the punishment should be reduced to merely two cows for the well. Guyyo, however insisted on claiming for some compensation. The *jallaaba* replied that he could be compensated by saving the cow he was supposed to give as a contribution for the well. The *huyyu* also disagreed with the *jallaaba* and persisted in claiming at least two cows.

At this point the whole assembly, addressing the *hayyu*, repeated in a loud chorus: "*Horaa bula, horaa bula, deebanu*". This is a typical formula of blessing used very often in assemblies in order to exercise pressure over individuals, especially when one has to submit himself to some form of sacrifice on behalf of the community. In fact the individual receives a blessing as a compensation for his sacrifice. The meaning is, more or less, "May you live long and wealthy, may your people multiply", and it clearly is a codified form of expressing the will of the assembly. The *hayyu* gave up his claim and, in this way, he was able to obtain once again the blessing of his clan.

The discussion then turned to the two cows for the well and, this time, it was the *abbaa eelaa* (father of the well) who had to decide on them. Lastly, the *abbaa eelaa* renounced one cow and claimed only the other one. At the end, the *hayyu* spoke again saying that Anna had to give one cow for the well, whereas Guyyo was not expected to give any.

This last statement of the *hayyu* may be considered the final decision: in fact, soon after, the assembly's attention was turned to other subjects. During all the phases of penalty reduction Anna never spoke. The general atmosphere was cheerful, like a collective joke at the expense of Anna.

Subsequently, I witnessed many similar cases of forgiveness, both during the same meeting and in other assembly contexts. I could thus verify that the procedure of penalty reduction always occurs after the culprit pleads guilty, and always through the ritual just described.

The conventional and almost automatic character of the procedure is underlined by the fact that the ritual formula for asking forgiveness is itself a way of declaring oneself guilty. Therefore, we can speak of "institutional forgiveness".

The primary aim of the Borana judicial system - as in the case of the village tribunals of the Nyoro described by Beattie⁵³ - is not punishment itself, but rather the reduction of social tension and resentment. When a quarrel is discussed in the context of an assembly, there is always a first phase of clarification, during which each side's position is explained and latent tension is slowly dissolved, eventually leading to a reciprocal understanding. Aggression and open anger should carefully be avoided both in behavior and in speech.

The numerous interventions of the participants constantly conveys an idea of the opinion which the audience is forming. This first phase may last from a few minutes to a few days and it may eventually continue during a subsequent assembly. It ends with the sentence by the *hayyu*, a *super partes* judge, whose role is to explain the laws and the modality of a proper punishment. The *hayyu*'s legitimacy comes from his long and specific apprenticeship in the ceremonial villages relating to institutions such as *galila* and *gadaa* system.

⁵³ J. Beattie, 1960, p. 69.

The phase of penalty reduction will then follow, but only if guilt is recognised. A fine can be reduced only on condition of crying for mercy in a ridiculous way. The degree to which this behavior is required is probably proportional to the resistance shown during the previous phases. If the injured party fails to forgive, the assembly as a whole will claim it by its power of blessing.

As a final result the injured obtains his public satisfaction and the offender his punishment, which will not be a terribly high fine, but rather a form of humiliation. This is not an uncommon situation in stateless societies. Radcliffe-Brown has pointed out the use of ridicule as a form of moral coercion and he distinguishes "satirical sanctions" from "penal sanctions"⁵⁴. The fact that through institutional forgiveness a penal sanction is converted into a satirical one seems more peculiar.

The real beneficiary of this process is the law itself, which can be proclaimed in all its dangerous penal potentiality - a powerful warning to everybody - thanks to the subsequent phase of forgiveness. Without this process it is very unlikely that this potential could in fact be actualised: individuals are always prepared to deny their guilt while heavy fines would require physical coercion to be implemented. Thus, while forgiveness is an institutional and necessary element of the judicial process, it appears to be granted only as compensation for admission of guilt.

It might be observed that informants have shown a tendency to underline the law itself rather than the process of forgiveness. This is perfectly in accordance with the objectives reached by means of institutional forgiveness, and hence with Borana values: the proclamation of the law with its warning effect.

References

- Barter, P. 1990.
"Oromo blessings and greetings", in A. Jacobson-Widding and W. van Beek (ed.),
The Creative Communion.
- Beattie, J. 1960
Bunyoro: an African Kingdom, London.
- Radcliffe-Brown, A. 1940
"Preface", in M. Fortes and E.E. Evans-Pritchard (eds.), *African Political Systems*,
London.

⁵⁴ A.R. Radcliffe-Brown, 1940, p. vii.